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Musculo-skeletal stress markers of the right tibia from Las Estalactitas cave: insights into the mobility during the Chalcolithic in Northern Spain

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To understand the biological changes shaped on human bones that the emergence of the first farming societies and the end of the hunter-gatherer lifestyle produced is of high interest. In the case of Northern Spain, despite the thousand funerary structures found in the Cantabrian region, few human remains have been recovered due to alkaline and acidic soils [1]. A recent study on two burial caves in the area integrating different methodologies [1] shows that the $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ and $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ isotope analysis indicates a predominantly C3 terrestrial diet, including animal protein (meat and likely dairy products) and $\delta^{34}\text{S}$ results show that not great distances were covered by these human groups, depending on locally mobility for their daily activities [1].

In this study we present the description of musculo-skeletal stress markers of the right tibia of a Chalcolithic ($3,955 \pm 75$ BP) skeleton from Las Estalactitas cave, intending to deepen into the mobility patterns of the first farmers during this crucial period. Las Estalactitas cave is located in Cantabria (Northern Spain), and the human remains were first discovered in 1928, and first studied in 1991 [2]. The skeleton is almost complete, and it belongs to a middle-aged adult male individual, characterized by advanced dental wear and an oral pathology [2]. Some bones are covered with a fine layer of calcrete, which makes it difficult for the proper study of bone surface.

To quantify the external shape of the tibia, we measured the Platycnemic Index of the tibial shaft according to Bass [3], and musculo-skeletal markers were recorded according to the *Standardised Scoring Method* proposed by Mariotti and collaborators [4]. Our results indicate that the right tibia is hyperplatycnemic (Platycnemic Index of 49.74), the quadriceps tendon has a medium development (1c), and the soleal line of the tibia (*musculus soleus*) has a high development (2) with the line of insertion marked and with rugosity. Besides, we found vascular grooves (the imprints of some lateral branches of the anterior tibial artery), that are more frequent in individuals with high levels of physical activity [5].

Our results support that these groups had a predominantly continuous movement in the region and maybe seasonal mobility related to animal transhumance could have increased the mobility of this Chalcolithic individual, developing the features analyzed. Further research will be carried out to shed some light to the daily activities of the first farmers in the Northern Iberian Peninsula.

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